

Morphological investigation of the photoactive layer in semitransparent organic solar cells

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Abstract

The narrow absorption range of organic semiconductors enables high semitransparency of organic solar cells (OSCs) in the visible spectrum. Typically, the active layer of OSCs consists of an interpenetrating network of donor and acceptor materials known as a bulk heterojunction. The effective separation of carriers at the interfaces between the donor and acceptor materials and their subsequent transport to the electrodes is crucial for device performance. Therefore, the size and distribution of the material phases, as well as their controlled manipulation during processing, are essential to achieve a high power conversion efficiency. As in large-scale fabrication, thicker films would be beneficial for defect-free deposition, we incorporate transparent fillers such as polystyrene into the photoactive layer to increase its thickness. However, this additional component has a significant impact on the morphology.

This work focuses on the morphological study of the photoactive layer in semitransparent OSCs by electron microscopy and atomic force microscopy. Although PTQ10 and BTP-FTh exhibit a high miscibility in BHJs without filler materials, PeakForce Kelvin Probe Force Microscopy measurements reveal a “mountain” structure caused by the additional filler material. The higher contact potential difference (CPD) of the “mountains” indicates a higher amount of BTP-FTh compared to the “valleys”.

Complementary Low-Energy Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy shows that donor-acceptor and donor-filler mixtures form highly miscible layers, while acceptor-filler layers tend to show agglomerations. Overall, the study of the morphology (e.g., see the below figure) provides key insights into the phase formation of the bulk heterojunction (BHJ) with incorporated filler material and highlight crucial parameters for the optimization.

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Figure: a) Topography and b) measured CPD of a BHJ with high amounts of a transparent insulator.